

Design And Implementation Of Digital Library System For Easy Accessibility To Teaching And Learning Resources In Katsina State Institute Of Technology And Management (KSITM), Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In the digital age, educational institutions need efficient ways to disseminate learning materials. This research proposes the development of a Digital Library System for Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management. The system aimed at facilitating the sharing of slide presentations and PDF files, enhancing accessibility and resource management among staff and students. The study focuses on designing and developing a Digital Library System specifically for Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management (KSITM). The system will facilitate the uploading, accessing, and managing of slides and PDF files, catering to the needs of staff and students at KSITM. The study will also analyze user requirements through interviews, questionnaire, surveys, and observations to create a user-friendly interface. The system will include features such as search functionality, user authentication, and secure file storage to enhance usability and security. The study will utilize PHP and possibly java script as the programming language and MySQL as the database management system to develop the digital library. The implementation phase will involve coding, integrating system components, and conducting thorough testing to ensure functionality and reliability.

Keywords: Digital age, PDF files, Digital Library, User Friendly Interface, Uploading, Downloading

INTRODUCTION

The advent of the digital era has revolutionized various sectors, including education. Traditional libraries, once the primary source of information and learning resources, are evolving into digital libraries. Digital libraries offer numerous advantages over their physical counterparts, including easy access, efficient

management, and the ability to share resources with a broader audience. Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management (KSITM) is an institution committed to providing high-quality education and fostering an environment conducive to learning and innovation. However, like many educational institutions, KSITM faces challenges in managing and distributing educational materials effectively. The traditional library system, though valuable, has limitations in terms of accessibility, resource management, and timely dissemination of information. To address these challenges, there is a need to develop a Digital Library System for KSITM. This system aims to enhance the accessibility and distribution of educational materials, particularly slides and PDF files, which are crucial for students' learning and academic success. By digitizing the library resources, KSITM can ensure that staff, students and other teeming members of the institute have seamless access to the necessary materials from anywhere and at any time. The proposed Digital Library System will leverage modern technology to create a centralized repository of educational resources. It will provide a user-friendly interface for uploading, accessing, and managing slides and PDF files. This system will not only improve the efficiency of resource management but also enhance the overall learning experience for students by providing them with the necessary tools to succeed in their academic pursuits. The implementation of a Digital Library System aligns with the global trend towards digitalization in education. Many educational institutions worldwide have successfully transitioned to digital libraries, resulting in improved access to information, better resource management, and enhanced academic outcomes. As an ICT based institution, adopting this approach, will position Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management (KSITM) as a forward-thinking institution committed to leveraging technology to enhance education.

Nowadays students of tertiary institutions are facing serious challenges in receiving and accessing a comprehensive and recommended lecture materials such as Pdf files, lecture slides and other reading resources from some of their course lecturers at a right time. These may cause several setbacks for the student's performance, which may lead to an unwanted increase in the student's failure rate, at the end of their semester result. Bhatt and Rana (2011) identified that the most common problems with e-resources are low speed connectivity, lack of accessibility, lack of awareness about statutory provision for accessing e-resources by the institutions, technical problems, unavailability of sufficient e-resources, doubts in permanency, high purchase price and lack of legal provision. This research work proposes an automated digital library system where all recommended Textbooks, Pdf files, Slide Presentation as well as many more educational resources will be uploaded so that any student and/or staff can use his login details to access and download each of the uploaded educational resources.

The major objectives of this proposed research work are as follows:

1. To design and implement a digital library system that enables the sharing of slides and PDF files between staff and students.
2. To provide an easily accessible repository for educational materials.
3. To improve the distribution and management of academic resources among staff and students.
4. To enhance the learning experience by ensuring timely and efficient access to study materials.

According to Pejova, (2016) launching and carrying out collaborative joint projects between professionals from developed countries and those from less developed countries as a way of developing information literacy skills which will enable students to acquire information retrieval skills that will enable them to exploit the massive e-resources that are in existence today. According to Katundu (2010), information literacy in the curriculum has not received much attention due to the factor that only librarians are engaged in the teaching of the library discipline.

Many authors such as Heseltine (2010) and Rader (2010), agree that a successful information literacy programme can be well delivered when it is integrated within curriculum. This is the only way that can be made to relate information sources to various courses, thus rendering it functional and more meaningful to students. Omoniwa (2013) observes that power will rest largely on staff that possesses multiple skills. Employment of librarians for instance, should be based on skills in technology applications. This strategy would improve on e-resource utilization, as academicians would be expected to provide computer

applications (Softwares) such as PDF files, Internet and CD-ROM technologies among others in enhancing students access to educational learning resources.

METHODOLOGY

The population of the study is the entire staff and students of Katsina state Institute of Technology and Management, the study will employ both the quantitative and qualitative perspectives. For the quantitative research element, the respondents will be requested to complete standard questionnaires on the way and manner they had been accessing and utilizing the teaching and learning materials in the existing system, and highlight the way and manner they wanted the proposed new system to be design and implemented.

On the other hand, the qualitative section of data collection, some selected staff and student of Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management (KSITM) will be engage with series of interviews and a survey study will also be conducted across the institute with the aim of getting true picture of the problem under study from the primary source.

The data collected from the sampled respondents from the distributed questionnaires, and the result of the interview conducted as well as the survey, will be analysed.

ANALYSIS OF EXISTING AND PROPOSED SYSTEM

Existing System

The current library and lecture material management system at the Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management primarily rely on manual and informal methods. Below are the features and challenges of the existing system:

Features of the Existing System

1. Manual Cataloging: Books and library resources are cataloged manually, often leading to delays in updating library records.
2. Physical Borrowing and Returning: Users must visit the library to borrow or return books, which is time-consuming and inconvenient.
3. Lecture Note Distribution: Lecturers share lecture slides and notes with students using flash drives, USBs, or WhatsApp groups. There is no central repository to store or distribute these materials, leading to inefficiencies.
4. Limited Accessibility: Library resources and lecture materials are not accessible online, restricting their availability to specific times and places.
5. Error-Prone Operations: Manual record-keeping is prone to errors, including misplaced records, duplication, and data loss.
6. Lack of Notifications: Users are not notified about due dates, fines, or availability of requested books, leading to missed deadlines.

Challenges with the Existing System

Lecture Slides Tracking: Lecture materials shared via flash drives or WhatsApp are difficult to track and often lost, especially in the absence of lecturers.

Inconsistent sharing methods lead to delays or incomplete access to learning materials.

Inefficiency: Manual processes for library and lecture note management consume time and increase the administrative workload.

Limited Access: Students cannot access books or lecture materials outside library hours or without direct interaction with lecturers.

Data Loss Risks: Paper-based library records and informal sharing methods for lecture notes are prone to loss or damage.

The Proposed System

The proposed Online Library System addresses the limitations of the existing system by integrating library and lecture material management. Key features and advantages include:

Features of the Proposed System

1. Digital Library Catalog: Books and other library resources will be digitally cataloged and accessible through a user-friendly online platform.
2. Lecture Notes Repository: A centralized system for uploading, storing, and sharing lecture slides and notes. Students can download materials directly from the system, reducing reliance on flash drives or WhatsApp.
3. User Accounts: Students and faculty will have individual accounts to access library resources and lecture materials.
4. Automated Borrowing and Returning: Users can request or return books online, with real-time updates to the library database.
5. 24/7 Accessibility: The system will be accessible from any location at any time, ensuring convenience for users.
6. Notification System: Automated notifications for due dates, fines, lecture material uploads, and updates.
7. Secure Data Storage: Lecture notes and library records will be securely stored in a database with regular backups.
8. Reporting and Analytics: Insights into book usage, lecture material access, and borrowing trends for informed decision-making.

Advantages of the Proposed System

Efficient Lecture Note Management: Lecturers can upload slides directly to the system, ensuring all students have access and eliminating the risk of losing materials.

Students can easily track and download lecture notes, even in the absence of lecturers.

Automation and Efficiency: Automation of library processes reduces administrative workload and enhances accuracy.

Improved Accessibility: Users can access library resources and lecture materials anytime, anywhere, fostering better learning experiences.

Data Security: A centralized system ensures secure storage of all data and reduces risks associated with loss or unauthorized access.

PROJECT WORKFLOW

The workflow for the development of the Online Library System follows a structured approach, ensuring that each phase contributes to achieving the project's objectives. The workflow is based on the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) and consists of the following stages:

1. Requirement Analysis

Conduct interviews and surveys with library staff, students, and faculty to identify system requirements.

Analyze the existing library management process to identify gaps and challenges.

Define the key features of the system, including online cataloging, book borrowing/return, user registration, and notification services.

2. System Design

Develop use case diagrams to model user interactions with the system.

Create system architecture to outline the structure of the database, server, and application.

Design wireframes and user interfaces (UI) to ensure a user-friendly experience.

Define database schema for storing information on books, users, transactions, and notifications.

3. Implementation

Develop the system using selected tools and technologies (PHP and JavaScript for programming; MySQL for database management).

Build front-end and back-end modules:

Front-end for user interfaces

Back-end for managing database

Integrate modules to ensure seamless functionality.

4. Testing

Perform the following types of testing:

Unit Testing: Test individual modules to ensure proper functioning.

Integration Testing: Check the interaction between modules.

System Testing: Validate the system as a whole against requirements.

User Acceptance Testing (UAT): Collect feedback from stakeholders and end-users.

Resolve bugs and refine features based on feedback.

5. Deployment

Deploy the system on a server for live access.

Provide training for library staff to manage and operate the system effectively.

Roll out the system for students and faculty, ensuring smooth transition from the manual process.

6. Maintenance and Updates

Monitor the system to ensure stability and performance.

Address user-reported issues and provide updates for new features or improvements.

Conduct periodic system reviews to adapt to changing library needs.

The project workflow follows a linear progression, as shown below:

Fig. 1.1 Showing the Project Workflow

SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT MODEL

The development of the Online Library System for Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management adopts the Waterfall Model of the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC). The Waterfall Model is chosen because it provides a structured and sequential approach to software development, which is suitable for projects with well-defined requirements.

Stages of the Waterfall Model

1. Requirement Analysis

Gather and document functional and non-functional requirements through interviews, surveys, and observation.

Identify key features of the system, such as user management, book cataloging, borrowing, returning, and notification services.

Define constraints, including budget, time, and technology limitations.

2. System Design

Develop a system architecture that outlines the relationship between system components.

Design the database schema to store user, book, and transaction data.

Create user interface (UI) prototypes to ensure usability and accessibility.

Prepare technical specifications for front-end and back-end development.

3. Implementation

Write the code for each system module using appropriate programming languages and frameworks.

Integrate the modules to ensure a fully functional system.

Perform initial testing to validate individual modules.

4. Testing

Conduct comprehensive testing, including:

Unit Testing: Testing each module in isolation.

Integration Testing: Ensuring modules work together as intended.

System Testing: Verifying the system against the initial requirements.

User Acceptance Testing (UAT): Collecting feedback from stakeholders and making necessary adjustments.

5. Deployment

Deploy the system on a local or cloud-based server.

Configure the system for operational use by library staff, students, and faculty.

Provide training to library staff on system functionalities.

6. Maintenance

Monitor system performance and resolve reported issues.

Implement updates and new features as needed.

Ensure data security and regular backups for reliability.

Justification for Using the Waterfall Model

Requirements are clearly defined and documented at the beginning of the project.

The sequential flow ensures that each phase is completed before moving to the next, reducing the risk of scope creep.

The model is simple to manage, making it ideal for projects with limited resources and strict timelines.

The technical design methodology for developing the Digital Library System for Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management (KSITM) follows a structured approach to ensure comprehensive analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. The methodology is divided into five main phases: Requirement Analysis, System Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation.

i. Requirement Analysis phase

To gather and document the functional and non-functional requirements of the Digital Library System.

Conduct interviews and surveys with students, lecturers, and staff to understand their needs and expectations.

Analyze current library processes and identify pain points and opportunities for improvement.

Develop a detailed requirements specification document outlining the necessary features and functionalities of the system.

ii. System Design phase

To create a detailed design of the Digital Library System, including the system architecture, database schema, and user interface.

Design the system architecture, specifying the components and their interactions.

Develop a user-friendly interface design, ensuring ease of utilization and accessibility.

Create an Entity-Relationship Diagram (ERD) and database schema for efficient data storage and retrieval.

Prepare wireframes and prototypes to visualize the system's interface and workflow.

iii. Development phase

To build the Digital Library System based on the design specifications.

Set up the development environment, including necessary tools and technologies (PHP, MySQL).

Implement the backend functionality, including user authentication, file upload/download, and database interactions.

Use Case Diagram of the System

Figure 1.2 Showing Use case diagram of the system

Software Development Model

Figure 1.3 Showing the System Development Model

Develop the frontend interface, ensuring responsiveness and usability. Integrate all system components and perform unit testing to ensure each module functions correctly.

Tools and Technologies

- Programming Language: PHP
- Database Management System: MySQL
- Development Tools: Integrated Development Environment (IDE), version control systems (e.g., Git)
- Testing Tools: Manual testing, automated testing tools
- Deployment: Web server (e.g., Apache or Nginx), hosting services

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This is the students sign up page

Figure 1.4 Student sign up page

This is the admin login page

The screenshot shows an admin dashboard with a navigation bar at the top containing buttons for 'Home', 'Add Book', 'Edit Book', 'Delete Book', and 'Logout'. Below the navigation bar is a table with the following columns: Book ID, Book Name, Book Author, Actual Copy, Available Copy, Department, and Ebook Name. The table contains 20 rows of data.

Book ID	Book Name	Book Author	Actual Copy	Available Copy	Department	Ebook Name
CS001	learning Python	Resma Therija	12	10	cs	CS001.pdf
CS002	Test Book	Test Author	12	12	cs	CS002.pdf
CS003	Test Book	Test Author	12	12	cs	CS003.pdf
CS031	learning java	Test Author	12	12	cs	CS031.pdf
CS005	Test Book	Test Author2	12	12	cs	CS005.pdf
CS006	Test Book	Test Author	12	12	cs	CS006.pdf
CS008	Test Book	Test Author	10	10	cs	CS008.pdf
CS009	Book One	Resma Therija	12	12	cs	CS009.pdf
CS010	Test Book	Test Author	10	10	cs	CS010.pdf
CS011	Test Book	Test Author	1	1	cs	CS011.pdf
CS012	Test Book	Test Author	1	1	cs	CS012.pdf
CS013	Test Book	Test Author	12	12	cs	CS013.pdf
EE001	Test Book	Test Author	12	12	ee	EE001.pdf
ME001	Test Book	Test Author	12	12	me	ME001.pdf
TT001	Book One	Test Author	12	12	tt	TT001.pdf
CS055	Test Book	Test Author	10	10	cs	CS055.pdf
B001	Let Us c	YK	10	10	cs	B001.pdf

Figure 1.5 Admin login page

This is the login page

Figure 1.6 login page

This is the downloading a book page

Figure 1.7 Down loading a Book

This is book editing page

Figure 1.8 Editing a Book

DISCUSSION OF RESULT

From the above result obtained, the outcome revealed that, the interfaces used are user friendly made up of different pages such as admin dashboard page where only admin can access and has privileges such as ability to edit and delete a book and/or lecture slides, Sign up page where students and staff can be able to register e.t.c

There are three (3) categories of users who can access the new system based on the privileges assigned to each one of them accordingly.

The first category is the admin, who is in charge of whole system. The admin has different privileges, among others is the ability to Upload a book and/or lecture slides, edit a book, Delete a book, Login and Logout.

The second category are the staff. Staff also where assigned with not less than five privileges of which are the ability to Sign Up, upload a book and/or lecture slides, Download a book and/or lecture slides, Login and Logout.

The third category are the students, who can be able to Sign Up, Download a book and/or lecture slides, Login and Logout.

RECOMMENDATIONS

After studying and considering the result of this project, the researchers recommended that:

1. The management of Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management should migrate from the existing manual system of accessing and distributing the educational/lecture materials between students and adopt this new system based on the fact that it is more reliable, fast and robust means of sharing educational resources among staff and students, which will definitely enhance effective teaching and learning process the Institute.
2. For the effective running of the online Digital library System (The new System) at Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management, stable power as well as stable and un interrupted Internet Access should be provided by the Government, at the Institute in order to ensure smooth and successful running of the new system.
3. The government should also provide ICT tools such as Computers, E-books, smart boards, projectors, educational softwares and any other modern ICT devices that will enhance instructional delivery in our educational institutions.
4. Seminars, workshops and routine training should be regularly organize in order to enable staff and students of the Institute to always be up to date in ICT knowledge and skills for effective and efficient instructional delivery.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, the study aimed at making an empirical research on the design and implementation of Digital Library System for easy distribution, accessibility and Utilization of teaching and learning materials at Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management for effective and efficient teaching and learning delivery. After following all processes, the major findings concluded that, automating the existing system (The manual system) with this new digital system will effectively enhance teaching and learning process by inculcating reading culture into the mind of staff and students of Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management and beyond.

REFERENCES

- Adewole, S. & Batagarawa, S. A. (2019). The use of E-library in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University library. *Middle Belt Journal of Library and Information Science* 11(1): 43-62.
- Adeyemi, B. M.. (2018). scholarly use of information for research by postgraduate students, therole of keneth dike (KDL) . *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 10(3), 19-26. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1666/>
- Afolayan, G.G. (2011). Amending the law establishing polytechnic for national technology emancipation. *Multidisciplinary journal of research development*, 17 (1) 1-6
- Awodu, Y.W. (2019). *Polytechnic education in Nigeria opportunities for wealth and job creation: The journey so far {Paper presentation at the 24th convocation ceremony of Federal polytechnic Idah}*. Kogi State, Nigeria on 11 May, 2019

- Edem, M. B. & Afebende, G. (2011). Developing digital libraries for improved academic information provision in Nigeria. *Library and information science practitioner*. 4(1 & 2), 313-323.
- Egberongbe, H. S. (2011). The Use and Impact of Electronic Resources at the University of Lagos. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 4(12), 20-28. Retrieved from webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbolin/egberongbe.html. on 20-10-2021
- Ekere, F.C. (2014). *Administration of academic libraries: A book of reading*. F.C. Ekere Praise House Publishers, Enugu State, Nigeria.
- Mole, A.J.C. (2019). *Practical Guide to Research in Library and Information Science*. Enugu, Enugu, Nigeria: UNN Pres
- Nwalo, K.I.N. (2006). *Collaboration in the Provision and Utilization of IT Facilities for Library and Information Science Education in Nigeria*. In: Information Technology in Library and Information Science Education in Nigeria.
- Sadiq, A.O (2016). Evaluating the use of polytechnic libraries in Nigeria: A case study of Federal polytechnic, Offa Library, Kwara State Nigeria, library, Kwara State Nigeria, *library philosophy and practice {e-journal}*, 12(41), 68-70. Retrieved at <http://digital.unl.edu/libphiprac>
- Tofi, S. T. & Fatafa, K. (2019). Availability, Accessibility and use of Electronic Information Resources for Research by Student in Francis Suleman Idachaba Library University of agriculture Makurdi Library Philosophy and practice.
- Tsakonas, G. & Papatheodorou, C. (2016). Analyzing and evaluating usefulness and usability in electronic information services. *Journal of Information Science*, 3(2), 400-419
- Oyewusi, F.O. & Oyeboade, S.A. (2009). *An empirical study of accessibility and use of library resources by undergraduates in a Nigerian state university of technology (PDF Download Available)*. Retrieved from:
- Shannon, M. O. (2009). *Qualifying Paper*. School of library & information science Indiana University, Bloomington.